

DIGIQUAKE: A DIGITAL GUIDE FOR ENHANCING LEARNERS' EARTHQUAKE DRILL IN MORONG NATIONAL SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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DigiQuake: A Digital Guide for Enhancing Learners' Earthquake Drill in Morong National Senior High School

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Abstract

Earthquake drills are paramount in academic institutions, these drills are used for testing the plans and knowledge of learners, teaching, and non-teaching personnel. With the previous conduct of earthquake drills in Morong National Senior High School, it was determined that the school still needs to improve its performance feedback from the School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Committee of the school. Ever since the implementation of the quarterly earthquake drill in the school, there are no available visual instructional materials. Thus a decline in the evaluation of earthquake drill performance. With the lack of teaching materials, the researchers came up with the DigiQuake digital interactive guide for enhancing the learners' conduct of earthquake drills. The study employed descriptive-developmental and experimental research design with the quantitative nature of research. Also, it followed the ADDIE model which refers to Analysis, Design, Develop, Implement and Evaluate. Six (6) DRRM-experts and seven (7) ICT-experts validated the DigiQuake digital interactive guide achieving a very satisfactory rating for content, instructional, and technical quality. The School Disaster Risk Reduction Committee evaluated the earthquake drill performance of learners with a very satisfactory result after the exposure. The posttest scores of learners increased after the exposure with a very high result.

Keywords: *digital guide, earthquake drill, interactive material*

Introduction

Disasters are inevitable, one cannot simply prevent a disaster. Among them are earthquakes, regarded as one of the most destructive ones out there. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), earthquakes caused approximately 750,000 deaths globally in the years 1998-2017 and 125 million people were affected during this period. In the Philippines, earthquakes are a natural occurrence thus considering it as an earthquake-prone country. The Philippine Institute of Volcanology and Seismology (PHIVOLCS) estimates around 100-150 earthquakes per year are felt and an average of 20 earthquakes a day. This is due to the country's geographical positioning, situated within the Pacific Ring of Fire.

Programs and seminars have always been the way to disseminate earthquake-related information. An educational program was employed in 22 schools in Nepal, and it was found out that it was effective in raising awareness levels however, risk perceptions did not change significantly (Subedi et al., 2020). Further, most of the students do not know the exit route and evacuation area of their school (Sanchez et al., 2019; Parlak et al., 2023). Nevertheless, designing a comprehensive educational program is crucial for preparedness (Torani et al., 2019).

The major problem that the Morong National Senior High School experiences is the poor practice of students during earthquake drills, learners perform earthquake drills without employing the duck-cover-hold instruction, others were near buildings prone to collapse in an actual situation, and these were the evaluation of the DRRM committee of the school. Data shows that the score of the 907 participants of MNSHS in "duck cover and hold" is 2 which is interpreted as "poor", while other parameters range from 1.2 to 4.2. Thus, if left unchecked, it may lead to detrimental effects in case of an actual earthquake.

Nowadays, digital applications and technologies are employed for earthquake and fire hazards that offer novel and far-reaching communication to inform communities to prepare or cope with extreme disasters, hence contributing significantly to disaster preparedness. The practical efficacy of digital applications in encouraging proactive hazard preparedness behaviors is still not yet proven (Verrucci et al., 2016). In the review, it highlights the failure to provide context-sensitive information that specifies and targets groups of users. With the analysis of different digital applications such as websites, Web, and mobile applications, this research aims to develop a school-based digital interactive guide that targets the needs of the users as done in the analysis phase of the study.

This study supports the 17 developmental goals of the World Health Organization (WHO), specifically the 11th goal "Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable" which underlines the topic of Disaster Risk Reduction, as well as the Digital Readiness Strategy of the NDRRMC of the Philippines which identified the need to optimize and promote digital resources and technology. This ensures that the study promotes and contributes to global action for sustainable development and digital readiness.

The DigiQuake digital interactive guide will include features to improve the conduct of earthquake drills, these are infographic modules, videos or animations, exit-route maps or evacuation maps, and hazard maps. Thus, this study aims to design, develop, evaluate, and test the school-centric digital guide in enhancing the learners' earthquake drill conduct for better resiliency.

Research Questions

The principal purpose of this study is to develop, validate, and test its effectiveness as a digital interactive guide for enhancing learners' earthquake drills. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the evaluation of the experts on the developed DigiQuake digital interactive guide for earthquake drills with respect to:
 - 1.1. DRRM-experts
 - 1.1.1. content quality; and
 - 1.1.2. instructional quality;
 - 1.2. ICT-experts
 - 1.2.1. technical quality?
2. How do the learners perform before and after exposure to the DigiQuake digital interactive guide for earthquake drills with respect to:
 - 2.1. earthquake drill; and
 - 2.2. pretest and posttest?
3. Is there any significant difference on the earthquake drill performance of learners before and after being exposed to the developed DigiQuake digital interactive guide for earthquake drills?
4. Is there any significant difference on the pretest and posttest performance of learners before and after being exposed to the developed DigiQuake digital interactive guide for earthquake drills?

Literature Review

Content Quality

In Disaster Risk Reduction education, an instructional material for guiding learners must consider the quality of the content for it bears the topics and lessons necessary for scaffolding the learners for resiliency. With the descriptions in the Guidelines and Processes for Learning Resource Management and Development Assessment and Evaluation for Localized Material, it describes that content should be accurate, up-to-date, logically developed and organized, free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias, and relevant to real-life situations. Also, content should stimulate critical thinking, and contribute to the mastery of the learning objectives (Division Guidelines and Processes for LRMS Assessment and Evaluation for Localized Materials, 2019).

In designing the content for disaster preparedness, cultural and linguistic factors must be considered as it is one of the important aspects of content design. Furthermore, disaster preparedness content can be customized for localized content. (Tarek, 2014). Thus, considering the contextualization of the digital interactive guide can aid learners in comprehending the topic more.

Ensuring content to be localized gives users operational and contextual relevance to their surroundings. School disaster preparedness and risk reduction vary from nation to nation with regard to the context and government capacity, moreover, the Comprehensive School Safety Framework (CSSF) where education resilience suggests developing teaching and learning materials with consideration of the learning outcomes and competencies to integrate disaster risk reduction in the conventional curriculum (George & Oliva, 2019). With this, the researchers can develop school-based content included in the DigiQuake digital interactive guide.

Furthermore, in the newest edition of the Comprehensive School Safety Framework 2022- 2030 one of the key responsibilities of Risk Reduction and Resilience Education is to ensure context-sensitive content and guidance for disaster risk reduction, response, and preparedness. Therefore, producing relevant and prudent inclusion of content for disaster risk reduction should be adhered to achieve a more resilient school community.

Instructional Quality

Instructional design of digital resources is often not crafted by abiding by the principles of design development (Leschenko et al., 2021), and a lack of evaluation and information regarding instructional design models are found (Abuhassana & Alnawajha, 2023). Hence, the use of the design principles of e-learning theory and the ADDIE model can ensure the development of quality instructional design of materials.

Also, in the Guidelines and Processes for LRMS Assessment and Evaluation for Localized Materials (2019) descriptions such as graphics/colors/sounds should be used for appropriate instructional purposes, and difficulty level should likewise be appropriate to the intended user.

Instructional material should abide by standards and screening before implementing it at school. Quality Review Tools of Instruction for Digital Learning Resources summarized that the digital material should be focused, engaging, and informative (NCDPI and Friday Institute-NC State University, 2020). Thus, ensuring instructional quality abides by the standards can effectively constitute a better learning experience.

Assessing the pedagogical aspect or the instructional aspect is necessary for an instructional learning resource. This involves the

assessment of purpose, objectives, and teaching strategies (Leschenko et al., 2021). This can be aligned with the study's instrument the LRDMs Rating Sheet for Non-Print Materials as it describes the material's purpose, objectives, and quality as an interactive resource.

Technical Quality

Technical quality allows a digital application to run and function properly for effective e-learning to happen. Employing expert evaluation of Screen Designs, Navigation, and User-friendly which can be associated with technical quality, in this evaluation IT experts judge the criteria regarding the developed android application in earthquake mitigation (Sukmawati et al., 2019). It can be connected with the study of Al-Sadi et al. (2022) which stated that emphasizing and enhancing functionality aligned with the usability of disaster management mobile applications will save lives and reduce costs. Thus, designing a digital guide should provide user satisfaction and user-centered experiences where the users' feedback is given attention.

Also, in the 2022-2030 CSSF developing quality teaching and learning material should ensure that the materials are accessible widely. This can be related to the criteria for evaluating a digital learning material, in the Quality Review Tools for Digital Learning Resources one of its domains is technological features wherein it describes that the material's feature should be accessible ((NCDPI and Friday Institute-NC State University, 2020).

Design and organization of the visuals, clear interface, technological innovation, and multimedia tools should determine the technical quality of a digital learning material (Leschenko et al., 2021). This suggests that the abovementioned aspects constitute to technological aspects in a quality digital learning material.

Digital Guide

Digital technology applications offer many possibilities in the new age including learning. The contribution of digital technology to context-specific disaster risk education is an important part of designing a sustainable and resilient community as it aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 11 of WHO (Mihoko & Shaw, 2022). Hence, the use of digital interactive guides can enhance the school earthquake preparedness and contribute to earthquake resilience in the school context.

Digital learning is both a trend and a challenge. ICTs in school do not have a direct and linear connection to the improvement of learning outcomes and PISA achievement. There is an ambiguous finding on the influence of ICT in schools (Bulman & Fairle, 2016). This indicates further investigation to determine the effect of ICT in academic institutions.

The primary advantage of digital learning resources is the customizability of student experience tailoring to the needs of the students. Digital resources merge different media together as what is known as multimedia. This was backed up by E-learning Theory which deals with the concept of multimedia effects to promote deeper learning (Soldani, 2022; Mayer et al., 2015).

When disasters occur printed hardcopy learning materials will inevitably get destroyed. After the devastating typhoon, Odette landed in the Dinagat Islands learning became a struggle, as the materials were destroyed (Trinidad & Osawa, 2023). Thus, digital solutions like the DigiQuake digital interactive guide for earthquake drills can aid in recovering the learning system even after a disaster strikes.

Earthquake Drill Performance

Students show a lack of concern for the occurrence of disasters, display a lack of involvement in disaster preparedness, have low awareness and knowledge about evacuation exits and evacuation areas of their school, and are absent of self-protection during seismic activity (Parlak et al., 2023).

Furthermore, it was highlighted that students do not utilize hardbooks to protect their heads and choose to independently evacuate during earthquake drills. This is observed in an earthquake simulation in Vigan City where it was highlighted in the evaluation that learners were advised to bring hard helmets and it was observed that participants executed the single-file formation instead of the "buddy-buddy" system during the evacuation phase (Villanueva, 2023). Therefore, DigiQuake's digital interactive guide aims to provide students with disaster preparedness and mitigation knowledge to equip students with proper earthquake preparedness procedures.

Two types of disaster exercises which are the discussion-based exercises and operations-based exercises. Both of them differ fundamentally, discussion-based exercises focus more on the seminars, orientations, and group discussions, while, operations-based exercises deal with drills, functional exercises (stressful simulated events), and full-scale exercises. Along with this, it also presented exercise evaluation wherein the functional exercises should be evaluated. This can be related to the study's orientation prior to the conduct of an earthquake drill in which learners are taught the procedures guided by the developed digital interactive guide.

Filipino earthquake preparedness studies are lacking. The Protection Motivation Theory and Extended Theory of Planned Behavior determined that the 727 respondents referred to media on their intention to prepare (Ong et al., 2021). With that, the DigiQuake digital interactive guide as a novel media for dissemination of earthquake drill preparedness will aim to address the problem as well as the recommendation of their study to make Filipinos conduct preparedness and mitigation practices.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a developmental-experimental research design along with the quantitative research method to determine the effectiveness of the proposed DigiQuake: A Digital Guide for Enhancing Learners' Earthquake Drill in Morong National Senior High School.

Participants

The study utilized the purposive and systematic sampling technique to determine the number of participants. Wherein, researchers select participants based on their expertise regarding a particular field.

Experts were chosen using the said purposive sampling. The researchers sought eight (6) DRRM experts to evaluate the application's content and instructional quality. Furthermore, eight (8) ICT experts are selected to evaluate the technical quality of the application. Along with their ratings, they also provided in-depth evaluation, comments, and recommendations for the development of the digital interactive guide.

Student participants are selected through systematic sampling which the grade 12 learners of Morong National Senior High School with a sample of 30 participants from academic and TVL track.

Instruments

The study adopted the rating sheet from the Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRMDS) Technical Specifications for Non-Print Resources by the Department of Education. Which primarily consists of content, instructional, and technical quality. The variables mentioned have a (4) four-point scale:

<i>Rating Scale</i>	<i>Scale Interval</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
4	3.28-4.00	Very Satisfactory
3	2.52-3.27	Satisfactory/Not Applicable
2	1.76-2.51	Poor
1	1.00-1.75	Not Satisfactory

In rating the performance of the learners' conduct of earthquake drill, the study referred to the National Disaster Risk Reduction Management Council and Office of Civil Defense earthquake drill evaluation form. In which the study only considered the part 1 general evaluation, this instrument consisted of a (5) five-point scale:

<i>Rating Scale</i>	<i>Scale Interval</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
5	4.21-5.00	Very Satisfactory
4	3.41-4.20	Satisfactory
3	2.61-3.40	Fair
2	1.81-2.60	Poor
1	1.00-1.80	Very Poor

The scale below is used for the pre-test and post-test performance of learners in the before and after exposure to the developed digital guide.

<i>Scale Interval</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
25-30	Very High
19-24	High
13-18	Average
7-12	Below Average
0-12	Poor

Procedure

The study followed the Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation in the making of the DigiQuake and the study's conduct. Firstly, the least mastered descriptions or competencies were taken into consideration using the data from the SDRRMC of the school. Then, the researchers designed the instructional material as a digital interactive guide with assistance from the SDRRM Coordinator. In the development process, the e-book will be developed using Kotobee Author, it is a platform where e-books can be created and it is an EPUB editor in which the researcher will also use Adobe Photoshop, a software published by Adobe, where you can create, design and edit images.

Furthermore, the validation was conducted in the development stage of the ADDIE model in order to identify errors and suggestions for improvement. After the validation phase, with approval from the research advisers, experts, and the adult sponsor, then the

researchers asked the potential participants their consent to conduct a study in order to disseminate and distribute the digital interactive guide to target users through google forms. With the learners now exposed to the digital interactive guide, the researchers requested approval addressed to the principal in conducting an earthquake to test the preparedness of students. Using the mentioned evaluation form the performance of the grade 12 learners is scored.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the study, research ethics are followed and adhered to guarantee the welfare, rights, and veracity of the participants. Hence, this study was guided by the principles of research ethics tackled at the National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences by Resnik (2020).

With that, the study ensured that the consent informed the respondent regarding the purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits of the study. Letters were sent to the experts requesting their expert assessment of the developed digital interactive guide. Moreover, the confidentiality of the responses was kept and managed prudently, keeping the identities and sensitive information hidden from the public.

Results and Discussion

Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed DigiQuake Digital Interactive Guide in terms of Content Quality

Table 1 on the next page shows the evaluation of the DRRM experts on the developed DigiQuake: A Digital Guide for Enhancing Learners' Earthquake Drill in Morong National Senior High School with respect to Content Quality. It could be noted that the items included in this variable were given a verbal interpretation of "Very Satisfactory" with a grand mean of 3.82.

The experts perceived the indicators of content quality of the DigiQuake Digital Interactive Guide as "Very Satisfactory" as reflected in their mean ratings ranging from 3.67 to 3.83. The experts consider the content of the digital interactive guide as consistent, accurate, up-to-date, logically developed and organized, objective, relevant to the procedures to be done in real life, and appropriate in terms of the language used.

As remarked by the MDRRMO coordinator "Checklist? Ahhh that's very good for the headcount!", when the researchers stated "Nagprovide po kami ng ano po ng sample checklist". which indicates that it is approved and accepted by the expert.

This result means that the developed DigiQuake Digital Interactive Guide is well crafted and has quality content, it is suited and relevant with the proper procedures as indicated in the content of the digital interactive guide for MNSHS learners.

It can be implied that the content of the developed DigiQuake Digital Interactive Guide can improve the awareness and preparedness of the grade 12 learners in MNSHS. With the use of quality content provided in the digital interactive guide being localized and school-based, the learners will understand the content of the developed digital interactive guide more efficiently, this supports the study of George and Olivia (2019), providing localized material allows learners to have contextual and functional relevance to their environment.

Table 1. Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed DigiQuake Digital Interactive Guide in terms of Content Quality

<i>Content Quality</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
2. Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	3.67	Very Satisfactory
3. Content is accurate.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
4. Content is up-to-date.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
5. Content is logically developed and organized.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
6. Content is free from cultural, gender, racial or ethnic bias.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
7. Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
8. Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
9. Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
10. Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.82	Very Satisfactory

Table 2 below shows the mean ratings from the perception of DRRM experts with regard to the content and instructional quality. In this, all specific qualities got very satisfactory results.

The experts rated the indicators of instructional quality of the DigiQuake Digital Interactive Guide as "Very Satisfactory" as reflected on their mean ratings ranging from 3.67 to 3.83. The instructional quality of the digital interactive guide is considered effective and

appropriate for the learners in MNSHS, as per the experts, it clearly conveys the purpose of the Digital Interactive Guide. The learning objectives are clearly shown and promote challenging and engaging instructions among the learners. It helps the learners bring out their creativity and explore the digital interactive guide.

The outcome means that the instructional quality of the DigiQuake digital interactive guide achieved the necessary instructions that are included in the procedures as shown in the digital interactive guide. Where it promotes creativity, enjoyable quality, and an interactive learning environment for learners to easily absorb knowledge crucial to being a well-informed and prepared individual.

With that, this implies the instructions included in the digital interactive guide will intrigue the interest of learners because the icons, graphics, and colors included will induce interest among learners, thus it will be clearly understood and enhance the skills as well as the mastery of learners in following instructions regarding earthquake drills. This is in line with the study of Akpi (2019), which states that written, graphics, and verbal are the three fundamental forms of communication in health safety. Also, it can be used as a teaching tool to effectively capture the interest of the audience and deliver a message

Table 2. *Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed DigiQuake Digital Interactive Guide in terms of Instructional Quality*

<i>Instructional Quality</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Purpose of the material is well defined.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
2. Material achieves its defined purpose.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
3. Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
4. Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	3.67	Very Satisfactory
5. Graphics/colors/sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
6. Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
7. Material effectively stimulates creativity of target user.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
8. Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
9. Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
10. Instruction is integrated with target user's previous experience.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.82	Very Satisfactory

Table 3. *Expert Assessment of the Developed DigiQuake digital guide as Evaluated by ICT experts with respect to Technical Quality*

<i>Technical Quality</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Audio enhances understanding of the concept.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
2. Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
3. There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
4. Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
5. Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
6. Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
7. Visuals sustain interest and do not distract user's attention.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
8. Visuals provide accurate representation of the concept discussed.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
9. The user support materials (if any) are effective.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
10. The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material	4.00	Very Satisfactory
11. The material can easily and independently be used.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
12. The material will run using minimum system requirements.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
13. The program is free from technical problems.	3.83	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.95	Very Satisfactory

Table 3 on the next page displays the evaluation of the ICT experts on the developed DigiQuake: A Digital Guide for Enhancing Learners' Earthquake Drill in Morong National Senior High School with regards to Technical Quality.

It could be pointed out that the components included in this variable were given a verbal interpretation of “Very Satisfactory” with a mean of 3.95.

The experts considered the indicators of the technical quality of DigiQuake Digital Interactive Guide as “Very Satisfactory” as shown in their mean ratings spanning from 3.83 to

The technical quality of the DigiQuake digital interactive guide contributed to the enhancement of audio, visuals, and overall design of the digital interactive.

With high functionality, the learners will be able to use the digital interactive guide effectively and easily. This also enables users to actively utilize the digital guide seamlessly, thus promoting a user-friendly environment for effective utilization of the digital interactive guide.

From there, it can be implied that the digital interactive guide constitutes effective management of the visuals, and features, such as navigation and hyperlinks that promote user-friendly quality. Furthermore, with the technical quality of the digital guide having very satisfactory results, it can be said that the DigiQuake

In the study of Sukmawati et al. (2019), employing expert evaluation with qualities like navigation, screen designs, and user-friendliness, will allow further improvements in order for the digital guide to function properly. Further relation by the study of Al-sadi et al. (2022) emphasizes that enhancing the functionality aligned with the usability of disaster management digital applications will save lives and reduce costs.

Table 4 on the next page shows the performance level of the grade 12 learners with respect to earthquake drill evaluation before and after exposure to the developed DigiQuake, a digital interactive guide. It could be noted that the overall evaluation before the intervention garnered a verbal interpretation “Fair” while the results after the intervention got a “Very Satisfactory” rating.

The table reveals that the evaluation of the SDRRMC perceived low-level performance of learners before the intervention is reflected by the range 1.2-4.2. In this, the participant’s execution of the response, evacuation, and assembly phases, got a score of 2.4, 2.8, 1.8, 2.2, and 2.4 respectively which shows a “Poor” performance rating. Whereas, the alarm, and headcount phase were rated as “Satisfactory” with 4.2, 3.6, 3.8, and 4.2 ratings.

Table 4. *Earthquake Drill Performance of Grade 12 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Developed Digital Interactive Guide*

General Evaluation	Before	VI	After	VI
1. The alarm system used is loud enough to be heard by all drill participants	4.2	S	5	VS
2. The drill participants executed the “duck, cover, and hold” technique during the Alarm Phase or while the alarm system is being sounded.	2.4	P	4.4	VS
3. The drill participants waited for the alarm system to stop before evacuating.	2.8	P	5	VS
4. The drill participants executed the “buddy-buddy” system during the evacuation phase.	1.2	VP	5	VS
5. The drill participants walked faster than normal during the evacuation phase.	1.8	P	3.4	F
6. The drill participants followed their evacuation routes to the evacuation area/s.	2.2	P	5	VS
7. The drill participants covered their heads while vacating the building.	2.4	P	4.2	S
8. The participants checked for any sustained injury in the evacuation/assembly area/s.	3.6	S	4.2	S
9. A headcount was conducted while in the evacuation area.	3.8	S	4.2	S
10. The participants stayed in the evacuation area until the drill was terminated.	4.2	S	5	VS
OVERALL	2.86	F	4.54	VS

It is quite clear that only item 5 on the “After” column received a rating of Fair (F) which means that only some of the learners walked faster than normal as observed by the SDRRM, it could be noted that indicating fast movement in the evacuation phase should be emphasized in the digital interactive guide. Moreover, the increase in ratings on item 4, which showed the greatest increase among the descriptions, entails that the emphasis of the DigiQuake digital interactive guide on the Buddy-Buddy system has influenced the performance of learners.

Further observation included the use of books and folders as head covers during the drill as evaluated by the SDRRM Coordinator. This may imply that in the video inculcated in the DigiQuake, learners followed and observed the use of a hard folder, hence the use of folders and books. This contradicts other previous evaluations from Villanueva (2023), which stated that students did not utilize hardbooks to cover themselves and that participants utilized the single-file formation rather than the buddy-buddy system

Table 5. *Pretest-Posttest Performance of Grade 12 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Developed Digital Interactive Guide*

Grade 12		Mean	SD	VI
Academic Track	Pre-test	17.20	4.74	Average
	Post-test	26.53	4.44	Very High
TVL Track	Pre-test	15.80	5.53	Average
	Post-test	20.20	6.18	High

On the other hand, Table 5 above shows the performance of learners with respect to the pre-test and post-test scores on the exposure to the DigiQuake digital interactive guide. With that, it could be noted that both groups had an increase in their test scores.

As revealed by the scores in the pretest, both academic and TVL learners got low scores, in which the academic students got a mean score of 18.41 while the TVL students garnered a lower score of 16.39. These were opposite to the post-test scores as they revealed higher scores in both fields respectively, garnering a mean score of 27.74 and 16.39.

This interpreted an increase in scores as a result of the intervention of the researchers. Further, it could be said that the developed DigiQuake digital interactive guide succeeded in its goal to enhance learners regarding earthquake preparedness.

Further implication can be made as the test scores of the TVL students also increased, which could entail that the intervention aided learners in teaching earthquake drill procedures and familiarizing them with the evacuation areas of the school.

The aforementioned implications are congruent with the study of San Jose, Ceninia, Medrano, and Salvan (2023) wherein state that integrating technology in a school environment makes learning effective. Therefore, the DigiQuake digital interactive guide is a digital learning resource that can aid learners in enhancing their conceptual knowledge regarding earthquakes and mitigation or response practices.

Table 6. *Significant Difference in the Earthquake Drill Performance Before and After Exposure to the Developed Digital Interactive Guide*

Group		Mean	SD	t	df	Sig	HO	VI
Grade 12	Before	2.86	0.58	11.48	4	0.00	R	S
	After	4.54	0.26					

Table 6 reveals that there is a significant difference in the evaluation of SDRRMC on the performance of learners regarding the conduct of earthquake drills before and after exposure to the developed digital interactive guide since the computed p-value of 0.00 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This implies that the exposure of the learners to the DigiQuake digital interactive guide yielded positive outcomes that suggest the use of multimedia in the content of the guide like videos, maps, infographics, and interactivities greatly helped learners digest information more effectively.

As stated by Mayer et al. (2015) and Soldani (2022) the concept of multimedia effects is aligned with the e-learning theory wherein it deals with the combination of audio, visuals, and texts in order to promote deeper learning. Therefore, the results of this study support the theoretical framework of the study which is the E-Learning theory that promotes integration of technology in learning.

Table 7. *Significant Difference in the Pretest and Posttest Performance Before and After Exposure to the Developed Digital Interactive Guide*

Grade 12		Mean	SD	t	df	Sig	HO	VI
Academic Track	Pre-test	17.20	4.74	7.90	14	0.00	R	S
	Post-test	26.53	4.44					
TVL Track	Pre-test	15.80	5.53	3.50	14	0.00	R	S
	Post-test	20.20	6.18					

Table 7 on the other hand revealed that there was a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the learners from the academic track and TVL track for which the computed p-values of 0.00 did not exceed the pre-specified alpha level of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected and was verbally interpreted as significant.

It can be said that the post-test scores from both groups of students had an increase in their mean scores. This can imply that the digital interactive guide is successful in helping learners to conceptualize earthquake its dangers and preparedness measures. This addresses a common problem shared with Parlak et al. (2023), that students display a lack of concern for the occurrence of disasters and disaster preparedness involvement as well as having low awareness and knowledge regarding exit-routes and evacuation areas of the school.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis of the results, it was concluded that the DigiQuake digital interactive guide was is valid, substantial, and functional as a digital learning material for earthquake preparedness as concurred by the experts with respect to content, instructional, and technical quality. The use of the digital guide significantly affected the performance of learners in both earthquake drill and pretest-posttest due to its interactive features like self-assessment, sounds, videos, scrollable infographics, checklists, and reflection.

Based on the conclusions, it was recommended to explore other potential content like typhoons, landslides, fires, and other hazards, have it used by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Committee (SDRRMC) for its orientation. Further implementations could be made to determine the extent of effectiveness of the digital guide in the school.

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